

**WP8 – Communication, Dissemination and
Exploitation**

**D8.3:
ENFASYS website**

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101059589.

Document Information

Grant Agreement Number	101059589	Acronym	ENFASYS	
Full Title	Encouraging Farmers towards sustainable farming Systems through policy and business Strategies			
Start Date	1 st Sep 2022	Duration	48 months	
Project URL				
Deliverable	D8.3 – ENFASYS website			
Work Package	WP8 – Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation			
Date of Delivery	Contractual	28 th of February 2023	Actual	
Nature	iReport	Dissemination Level	Public	
Lead Beneficiary	Association of Balkan Eco-Innovation (ABE)			
Responsible Author	Sara Matković			
Contributions From	Davide Guariento			

Document History

Version	Issue Date	Stage	Description	Contributor
1.0	22/02/2023	Draft	First full draft	Sara Matković, Davide Guariento

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1 Executive summary

The current deliverable presents the preliminary work done for the design and development of the first version of the project website.

The communication team, consulting with the coordinator, aimed to design a modern website that reflects the purpose of the project.

Thus, the scope of the ENFASYS website is to:

- Provide the project's visual identity and be always available to anyone,
- Be easily found through a search engine,
- Have a wider outreach than other more traditional means,
- Generate growth and deliver strong messages.

The website has been launched early in the project (M3) as a key instrument to support the growth of the project.

The website will be a “living” tool, thus it will be updated throughout the project.

2 Objectives

The website is one of the most important features of the project for the communication with all the different target groups.

Nowadays, it is a very common method of communication for multiple reasons. A well-organised and user-friendly website will target the audience to search even more, so a representative website is a key activity of any project. Apart from the fact that a website helps to spread the news faster, it has the power to educate and inspire people delivering strong ideas and values.

Within this framework, the ENFASYS website aims to stimulate interest in the project and raise awareness about the sustainable farming systems, while at the same time it allows the user to follow up the project achievements and results.

The design and development of the website was made considering certain objectives such as:

- **Inform the audience** about multiple actions including upcoming events, new technologies, and new innovations regarding sustainable farming systems,
- **Demonstrate the project:** The scope of the project and its results will be available to the wide audience through the website,
- **Communication channels:** linking to social media networks such as LinkedIn, Twitter, and Facebook.

The ENFASYS website is available at: <https://www.enfasysproject.eu/>

3 Website requirements

During the design and development of the project website, we took into consideration multiple requirements from a literature review on the best practices to render a successful website. We seek to assure it meets accessibility standards and is gender neutral following well-established guidelines. Moreover, requirements set by the EC in the project's Grant Agreement were met.

3.1 Accessibility requirements

It is crucial to create Web content more accessible to people with special requirements¹. These actions should take into consideration a wide range of sensitivities such as physical, speech, learning, visual, auditory, cognitive and neurological special needs. Multiple factors can be taken into consideration, indicatively:

- Colors: information conveyed in color must be available also in other visual ways,
- Videos with low or no background audio. There is a suggestion that any audio does not confuse those with hearing problems,
- Audio control: the sound should be started by action initiated by the user, not automatically,
- Sign language: this aims to enable people who are deaf or hard of hearing to understand the content of the audio track of synchronized media presentations,
- Text spacing enables to derive the right meaning,
- Only key board use: Navigation using only the keyboard helps those who have difficulties using devices as a mouse,
- Include heading and labels to describe topic or purpose / helps to better understand the content,
- Web pages should appear and operate in predictable ways to increase visitors' focus.

According to these requirements, the ENFASYS website was built in a structure that it is easy for the visitor to navigate. It has a traditional form and it operates in predictable ways, something that does not distract the visitor's focus. Furthermore, the videos that were integrated in the website have no audio, so will not limit the experience of visitors with hearing problems. All images and subpages are labeled and organized, so that visitors can easily find the information they seek, understanding the relationships between different parts of the content. This is especially helpful to those who read at a slow pace or have short-term memory. In the ENFASYS website the text spacing was also carefully chosen, as people with low vision require increased space between lines, word and letters in order to read the text.

3.2 Gender requirements

The ENFASYS consortium has been committed, since at an early stage of the project, to actively promote gender equality and pay the relevant attention to gender aspects and issues during the project implementation. For that reason, certain requirements have to be met in order for the ENFASYS website to be gender neutral and fulfil the provisions for equality among women and men for maximizing the impact the website has as a central dissemination tool.

Psychological and evolutionary studies have suggested a difference in how women and men see and process information. Notable examples are in color, word usage, and shapes which either due to genetic or psychological reasons, are perceived differently by individuals of different gender.

¹ Web Content Accessibility Guidelines (WCAG) 2.1, <https://www.w3.org/TR/WCAG21/>

There are distinct elements in a website interface design that will be preferred by either men or women, and websites can be made to specifically target one gender using these principles. According to literature the essential elements of a gender-neutral website are:

- Nature imagery in background and present throughout interface,
- Rounded corners, but less so than a female biased interface,
- Minimal language use, and in a casual but non-conversational tone when in use. It is obvious that special care must be taken to the use of gendered language,
- A mix of widely placed content but in a vertical scrolling area in browser friendly fields.

Further elements of a gender-neutral website related to color are:

- The use of strong contrasts between any background color and the overlying text,
- Background behind text solid and plain,
- One dominant color in headings and borders with bright tones are better,
- Visual interest can be provided with contrast colors complementary or closely related to the website dominant color,
- Colors that closely relate to primary or secondary colors when possible, can be selected,
- Color elements such neon, pastel, dark, discordant, or unusual should be avoided.

Taking into account these requirements, the ENFASYS website attempts to overcome and go beyond any existing gender norm by providing an innovative website interface design that includes a synthesis between male- and female-targeted interface designs in order to provide a gender-neutral user experience. However, it has to be noted that even if much care and attention is given to this topic, there is no single recipe in approaching gender issues that have an inherent subjective aspect. Before going online, the ENFASYS website design has been assessed both by male and female professionals. Further assessment of the website design will be provided during the project implementation and the appropriate modifications will be applied when and where needed.

3.3 Requirements from Grant Agreement

According to the Grant Agreement, the project communication team is required to design an attractive and informative website as the main point of reference about the project. The website should introduce the project website offering access to downloadable material and providing updates on its activities. All the public results created within the project should be available through the website, including deliverables, promotional videos, material from training and business events, etc.

The website was designed according to the obligations set by the EC. Thus, it displays the EU emblem and the statement that the project has received funding from a specific EU programme under a specific grant agreement number in a prominent place.

4 Website design and content

4.1 Website design

From the very beginning of the project, the domain for the project was bought for the next years: <https://www.enfasysproject.eu/>

This selection was made to ensure that all the interested stakeholders could easily find ENFASYS's website.

An e-mail account which the public will be able to address for any issue relevant to the ENFASYS project has been created: info@enfasyproject.eu. This account will be included in all used dissemination tools, such as the project website, social media accounts, printed material, etc. The ENFASYS website is running in WordPress, which is a popular, well-supported publishing platform that is supported by a wide community of developers which will minimize the complexity of the ongoing design. The first task concerning the website design was the selection of the most appropriate template that could cover the needs of the project. After a thorough research and brainstorming, the communication team agreed on a website template that is modern and dynamic, and offers the opportunity for continuous modifications. Having a sitemap that is constructed with a clear goal in mind could be a driving factor to a website's success. This is due to the fact that a well-structured sitemap will make a site easily searchable by, and will provide visitors with more accurate results when they are looking for keywords or key terms that are associated with it. The site crawlers used by search engines depend on sitemaps to point visitors in the direction of the correct website. According to the sitemap provided by the communication team, a graphic designer designed some mockups of the website, on which the communication team brainstormed and made modifications.

HOME ABOUT THE PROJECT MEDIA RESULTS SUMMER SCHOOL CONTACT US

Finding effective policy interventions and business strategies that can support farmers towards more

Sustainable Farming Systems

Figure 1 ENFASYS website mockup

After this procedure, the final version of the website interface was designed. The website has been designed in an easy way to navigate that allows users to learn about the ENFASYS project, the provided services, and the delivered results. There are sections that were foreseen in the website and are developed in the backend, but until all necessary content is available, they cannot be visualized. In the sections below we are presenting the different pages of the project website that are already available to the public.

4.2 Content

Currently, the ENFASYS website is comprised of the following sections:

- LANDING PAGE / Home

Main tabs

- ABOUT THE PROJECT
- MEDIA
- CONTACT US

The content will be regularly updated when a milestone is reached.

4.2.1 Home

(Goal: ensure clarity and understanding of the project in one glance) / from the top to bottom of the website:

- ENFASYS (name, one sentence description and goal of the project) 6 main quadrants (2 or 3 per line) to introduce the six key project pillars:
 - Scoping and framing. Scoping and framing transitions to SFS, based on a conceptual framework, a literature review and a light touch review of up to 160 cases of transitions to more SFS.
 - Understanding. Uncovering lock-ins from a systemic and behavioural point of view, through qualitative quantitative systems analysis, and qualitative-quantitative behavioural and experimental studies.
 - Creating ToCs. Combining systemic and behavioural insights regarding lock-ins and levers for SFS into empirically grounded and validated ToCs.
 - Testing interventions. Testing the potential of policies and business strategies to move farmers towards more SFS, through experimental studies (discrete choice experiments, field experiments and randomized controlled trials) and system dynamic modelling.
 - Designing solutions. Co-designing policy mixes, business strategies and social innovations and stimulating their implementation.
 - Achieving impact. Maximizing our impact by identifying clear pathways from results to outcomes, through strategic communication/exploitation/dissemination and tailored capacity building, and outcomes to impact, by contributing to key ongoing activities/initiatives on the local and European level.
- On and off banner about important upcoming events
- Key project target groups
- Links to social media (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter, YouTube) and social media box
- Terms and Conditions

Finding effective policy interventions and business strategies that can support farmers towards more

Sustainable Farming Systems

TARGET GROUPS

Who is this project for?

FARMERS Minimise pressure on ecosystems, while restoring and enhancing biodiversity	POLICY MAKERS Provide consumers with affordable, safe, traceable healthy and sustainable food	RESEARCH AND EDUCATION Enhance development of sustainable farming systems	FOOD CHAIN ACTORS Generate fair economic returns for farmers.	CONSUMERS AND NGOS Dissemination of information gathered across the project activities

About The Project

ENFASYS will frame current transitions to SFS and screen 160 cases for current interventions. Through systems analysis, behavioural and experimental studies, ENFASYS will uncover lock-ins from a systemic and behavioural point of view.

Media

ENFASYS will produce extensive video material, such as webinars and recorded podcasts, to widely communicate its findings. Check all the available material.

No Upcoming Events...

PROJECTS
Learn More About Us!

Get in touch

10
USE-CASES WITH REGIONAL SUSTAINABLE FARMING SYSTEMS

25
PEER-REVIEWED PAPERS

>100
WORKSHOPS WITH KEY PROJECT TARGET GROUPS

Figure 2 Landing page

The footer of the website is static for all the different subpages and present the same information. Links to social networks, presented by its logos, and there is a clear disclaimer about the project funding accompanied by the EU emblem. Finally, the copyright of the website and a link to its Privacy Policy are included in the footer.

Figure 3 Footer

4.2.2 About the project

(Goal: provide in detailed understanding about the project and its official documents)

- Project information, partners descriptions, Work Packages, FAQs

This section includes the information about the project's work packages, six key pillars as well as the partners consortium logos, on which when clicked, leads to their website.

Project key Work Packages

WP1 Scoping and Framing of pathways towards SFS
Objective: scope and frame the conducted research on systemic mechanisms, behavioural factors and experiments with proposed interventions, by building on previous research and connecting with ongoing research projects.

WP2 Developing a system-dynamic understanding of mechanisms, lock-ins and levers in the broader food system
Objective: uncover the key lock-ins and potential levers at the food system level to transition towards SFS throughout the EU and associated countries.

WP3 Understanding behavioural factors in the decision making of farmers and the buying behaviour of products from SFS
Objective: identify a comprehensive set of behavioural factors related to farmer decision-making towards different interventions options across case studies and at EU-level and ii) explore the buying behaviour of products from SFS of citizen-consumers

WP4 Develop systems- and behavioural based ToCs to understand the potential impact of public and private interventions
Objective: identify potential leverage points and strategies to effectively incentivise large-scale and long-term behavioural shifts by farmers towards SFS.

WP5 Test the potential of systemic and behavioural interventions through experimental research and system dynamic modelling
Objective: test the co-created systemic and behavioural interventions through experimental research and system dynamic modelling.

WP6 Enhancing policy design and implementation for climate neutral and sustainable EU farming systems
Objective: define transformative strategies for policy design and implementation to foster the shift towards SFS.

WP7 Develop business strategies, models a social innovation that collectively incentivise farmers to move towards SFS
Objective: propose business strategies, new business models and social innovation that engage farmers, consumers, and other food system actors in innovative ways to enable farmers to move towards more SFS.

Six Key Pillars

- SCOPING AND FRAMING**: Scoping and framing transitions to SFS, based on a conceptual framework, a literature review, and a light touch review of up to 100 cases of transitions to more SFS.
- UNDERSTANDING**: Uncovering lock-ins from a systemic and behavioural point of view, through qualitative quantitative systems analysis, and qualitative-quantitative behavioural and experimental studies.
- CREATING THEORIES OF CHANGES**: Combining systemic and behavioural insights regarding lock-ins and levers for SFS into empirically grounded and validated ToCs.
- TESTING INTERVENTIONS**: Testing the potential of policies and business strategies to move farmers towards more SFS, through experimental studies (lab-scale choice experiments, field experiments) and randomized controlled trials) and system dynamic modelling.
- DESIGNING SOLUTIONS**: Co-designing policy mixes, business strategies and social innovations and stimulating their implementation.
- ACHIEVING IMPACT**: Maximising our impact by identifying clear pathways from results to outcomes, through strategic communication (engagement), dissemination and before capacity building, and outcome to impact, by contributing to key ongoing activities/initiatives on the local and European level.

Project partners:

ILVO, CEJA, The Department of Nature Conservation, Gaia, MBS, NIBIO, UCLouvain, Institut de l'élevage IDELE, eagase, HELMUT HEINRICH UNIVERSITÄT DUISBURG, UNIVERSITÄT WÜRZBURG, FiBL

Sister projects:

BEATLES (BEHAVIOURAL CHANGE TOWARDS Climate-Smart Agriculture), visionary (Towards more sustainable food provision)

Figure 4 About the project page

4.2.3 Media

(Goal: provide easy access to the media/digital material produced during the project. Particularly aimed to young audience who is used to consume video-based material)

- Webinars, podcasts, live streamed events, photos, blogs, and press releases.

A well-designed media page is a critical brand-building tool for the project. This page is built to boost credibility.

Figure 5 Media page

4.2.4 Contact

- Contact us template.

This is the main page where visitors can find information to contact the ENFASYS team and ask for support. Association of Balkan eco-innovation as the leader of the work package 8 will be responsible for providing support through the project's email address. If needed, enquiries, comments, and information will be forwarded to project partners if necessary.

enfasys

HOME ABOUT THE PROJECT MEDIA CONTACT

Have Question?
Get In touch!

First Name *

Last Name *

Organisation

Subject *

Message *

SUBMIT

Figure 6 Contact page

4.3 Future tabs

Together with the growth of the project, the website will grow as well.

New tabs will be added:

1. Results
2. Training
3. Use-cases – the need of this tab is still being analyzed.

4.3.1 Results

(Goal: display all the main documents that summarize or analyse the project results/recommendations)

- Policy briefs, link to ResearchGate project page, factsheets, project results, public deliverables.

4.3.2 Training

(Goal: promote ENFASYS summer school)

- Includes the MOOCs and the summer school.
- Description and objectives of the school, start and ending date of the schools, place where it will take place, courses that will be part of the school, link to platform if online, access to media etc.

5 Conclusion

The ENFASYS website that was launched in M3 is a first version of the projectwebsite. Taking into consideration that the website is a “living” tool, it will be regularly updated. The website was designed and developed taking into consideration the specific needs of the visitors that should be addressed, the branding guidelines that were created by the ENFASYS communication team, the ease of accessibility and navigation through multiple layers, gender neutrality, the Grant Agreement requirements, and finally the helpfulness of the content, since it should be informative and help visitors better understand what ENFASYS is about.

End of Document

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101059589.